

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Project Title	The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns
Project Acronym	VeriFish
Project Number	101156426
Type of project	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01
Starting date of Project	01 May 2024
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.verifish.info

D3.3 – VeriFish media products requirements & specification document

Work Package	W3 Communication outreach campaigns & prototype media products
Task	T3.2 Requirements gathering phase for outreach media products
Lead author	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)
Contributors	Sabrina Duri (Trust-IT), Alessandro Petrocelli (COMMpla), Christine Absil (Clupea), Michelle Boonstra (Clupea), Tracy Murai (Poseidon), Tim Huntington (Poseidon), Yannis Marketakis (FORTH), Sian Astley (EUROFIR), Karl Presser (Premotec), Themis Altintzoglou (NOFIMA)
Peer reviewers	Karl Presser (Premotec), Oda Bjørnsborg (NOFIMA), Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)
Version	V1.0 - DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
Due Date	30/04/2025
Submission Date	30/04/2025

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public, fully open
	SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
	Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Funded by
the European Union

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	20/03/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Requirements gathering session and input collection
0.2	10/04/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	ToC and first version
0.3	18/04/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, Sabrina Duri (Trust-IT), Alessandro Petrocelli (COMMpla), Christine Absil (Clupea), Tracy Murai (Poseidon), Tim Huntington (Poseidon), Yannis Marketakis (FORTH), Sian Astley (EUROFIR)	First complete version for review
0.4	25/04/2025	Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)	Internal review, section
	28/04/2025	Karl Presser (Premotec), Oda Bjørnsborg (NOFIMA)	Internal review
1.0	29/04/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Final version

Keywords

VeriFish; VeriFish media products; aquafood sustainability; seafood sustainability; seafood, communication, seafood types, seafood consumers, communication strategies, fisheries, fishery, capture seafood; aquaculture, farmed seafood; communication materials; posters; card games; board games.

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafood repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ASC	Aquaculture Stewardship Council
CCBY	Creative Commons Attribution license
CoP	Community of Practice
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	Fisheries Improvement Project
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
MSC	Marine Stewardship Council
NGO	Non Governmental Organisation
OGS	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
SoMe	Social Media
STECF	Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The VeriFish project aims to develop a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators, a prototype app, and a EU Good Practice recommendation and will create and distribute a range of media products to be distributed for free among a selection of the VeriFish stakeholders, and run outreach campaigns to inform and promote these assets among these stakeholder groups, as well as raise consumers' awareness about how to “choose sustainable seafood” based on scientifically verifiable indicators.

Within this context, WP3 is designing and prototyping several easy-to-use media products including:

- *Flashcards and Board games*: Educational tools for children and adults to promote ocean health and sustainable seafood choices. The goal is to communicate people about the importance of ocean health through sustainable seafood choices.
- *Maps and Calendars*: Raising awareness about sustainability and supporting informed seafood choices.
- *Educational Posters*: Educational posters about seafood . These posters will focus on sustainability topics and highlight the importance of supporting local providers.

Additional media products that will be developed by VeriFish are *a children's recipe book* created in collaboration with nutritionists and food experts, and the *VeriFish Guidelines* providing user communities and key stakeholders (i.e., policymakers) with guidelines on the use of verifiable seafood indicators to improve communications about their products. These are described in two dedicated deliverables (*D2.3 Guideline for the use of seafood verifiable indicators* [August 2025 and *D3.8 VeriFish recipe book* [January 2026]) and are not included in this deliverable.

This deliverable presents the preliminary list of requirements and specifications gathered during a series of meetings organised to explore needs and expectations.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
1. Introduction	7
1.1. Links with other deliverables	8
1.2. Structure of the deliverable	8
1.3. Note for the reader: aquafood vs seafood	8
2. First requirements gathering workshop	9
3. Overview of VeriFish media products	10
4. Identified target users for the media products	11
4.1. SG1: Seafood Retailers & HoReCa	12
4.2. SG2: Consumers and consumer associations	13
4.3. SG3: Children via parents and educators	14
4.4. SG4: European Citizens	14
5. Benchmark analysis: other similar media products	15
5.1. Examples of educational materials	16
5.2. Games	19
5.3. Puzzles	25
5.4. High-level outcomes and considerations	26
6. Preliminary requirements	27
6.1. Species considered for the media products	27
6.2. Acknowledgement of VeriFish data sources	30
6.3. Recommendations from D4.1	30
6.4. Posters	30
6.5. Calendar	36
6.6. “Fishy businesses” flash card game	40
6.7. Map of fishery puzzle	42
6.8. Board game	44
7. Promotion and distribution channels	51
8. Next steps	55

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: VeriFish partner meeting in Crete, March 2025. The first requirements gathering session for the media products was organised in that remit, on March 20th.	9
Figure 2 Extract of the FigJam board used during the first requirements gathering session in Crete	10
Figure 3: Four stakeholders identified by the VeriFish project which are the target of the media products	12
Figure 4: screenshot of the list of media products analysed	15
Figure 5: Mr GoodFish recommendations for aquaculture - seasonal recommendations poster	17
Figure 6: The BlueMissionMed children’s book “Our Blue Treasure”	18
Figure 7: example of Nature Challenge cards game with aquatic animals	21
Figure 8: Puzzle 200 pieces. Observation of the world	26
Figure 9: List of Fishing Gear types by picture as included in the FAO Fact Sheets	33
Figure 10: sample skeleton of the VeriFish calendar, digital 16:9 widescreen format	39
Figure 11: Example of a draft mockup of Fishy businesses cards - the image is purely indicative	42

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1: Apparent consumption of top-15 most consumed products (2022). Source: EUMOFA, based on EUROSTAT.	28
Table 2: Example of 12 months distribution of fish sustainability related information	37

1. Introduction

Within the VeriFish indicator framework, information about sustainability, provenance, and nutrition will be available in one place. To help disseminate this information to citizens - both adults and children - media products will be published with the aim of translating the inherent complexity of seafood supply chains, health benefits and risks, and climate impacts using easy-to-understand materials. These will be white-labelled (limited branding) under CCBY licenses to promote re-uses by multiplier networks and further exploitation in a series of outreach campaigns.

Media products are being designed following a content multiplier approach. Factsheets collecting data and insights from the indicator framework for each species will be adapted and re-used to deliver content for a range of media products including:

- *Flashcards and board games*: Educational tools for children and adults to promote ocean health and sustainable seafood choices. The goal is to inform people about the importance of ocean health through sustainable seafood choices.
- *Maps and Calendars*: Raising awareness about sustainability and supporting informed seafood choices.
- *Educational Posters*: Educational posters about seafood to be distributed for free. These posters will focus on sustainability topics and highlight the importance of supporting local providers.

Leveraging on the same content, additional materials will be designed, such as *guidelines for the use of verifiable aquafood indicators* targeting user communities (e.g., retailers, consumer associations, seafood producers) and stakeholders (e.g., policymakers); *a children's recipe book* created in collaboration with nutritionists and food experts; and, ultimately, *a prototype web application* to search for sustainable seafood across 50 countries, accessible for in 24 languages, with a responsive design. In this way, the information contained in the indicators will be exploited and reused to higher potential, and awareness created based on data that only the VeriFish consortium can offer. As CCBY white-labelled outputs, these products can be -rebranded by user communities targeting consumers, ensuring future replicability and sustainability of these products. The guidelines, recipe book, and web app are subject of other deliverables, namely *D2.3 Guideline for the use of seafood verifiable indicators* (August 2025), *D3.8 VeriFish recipe book* (January 2026), and *D3.2 VeriFish web app requirements & specification document* due (April 2025), and are therefore not described in this deliverable.

To design media products that fully meet the needs of stakeholders, two additional feedback gathering workshops will be organised with the consortium and with seafood producers, as well as representatives from consumer associations, the members of the VeriFish EAB, in conjunction with web-app validation workshops. The aim is to validate the suggested approach to design the products, agree on the information gathered, focus on integration of all outputs by the project and clarify the dissemination towards the VeriFish Community of Practice and other channels.

1.1. Links with other deliverables

The value add of VeriFish media products relies on the fact that all the data sources that are used come from trusted and verifiable data sources, as presented in the VeriFish indicator framework. This deliverable therefore relies on the outcomes included in *D2.1 Indicator framework defined*¹ and *D2.2 Indicator framework developed* [due in April 2025], *D2.3 Guideline for the use of seafood verifiable indicators* [August 2025]. It is also linked to deliverable *D4.1 Initial recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood* [due in April 2025], *D3.2 VeriFish web app requirements & specification document* [due in April 2025] and *D3.8 VeriFish recipe book* [due in January 2026].

1.2. Structure of the deliverable

The **Introduction (Chapter 1)** sets the objectives of the document and clarifies the links with other deliverables produced so far. **Chapter 2** introduces the approach taken during the first requirement gathering workshop organised, first of a series of additional feedback sessions that will follow up once the prototype products are designed. **Chapter 3** gives an overview of the VeriFish media products that the consortium decided to work on, while **chapter 4** presents the sub-set of stakeholder groups that the media products will target, among the eight stakeholder types that VeriFish is targeting. In **chapter 5** the results of a benchmark analysis conducted across 40+ similar media products are presented. **Chapter 6** represents the core of this deliverable and details the preliminary requirements collected to design the media products, namely posters, card games, a map, a puzzle and a board game. It provides specifications with respect to the species considered for the media products, how to acknowledge the data sources, and lists the individual materials that will be realised, provisioning specifications with respect to formats, design, language and regional approach, accessibility of the products and seafood sustainability aspects will be at the core of the narrative / game in each of them. **Chapter 7** lists the promotion and distribution channels where the VeriFish media products will be distributed, and **chapter 8** gives some concluding remarks and introduces the next steps.

1.3. Note for the reader: aquafood vs seafood

In VeriFish the term “seafood” is used in communication campaigns and materials, while the term “aquafood” is normally used for deliverables and technical documents. In this deliverable we use the term “seafood” to refer to all edible organisms that inhabit aquatic environments. This includes food from fisheries and aquaculture, from seawater, brackish water and freshwater.

¹ Astley, S. (2024). VeriFish Indicator Framework defined- D2.1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14384281>

2. First requirements gathering workshop

The first requirement gathering workshop was organised in Heraklion, Crete, on the 20th of March 2025 in conjunction with the second VeriFish consortium meeting. The meeting was led by Sara Pittonet, Trust-IT, leading Subtasks 3.4.3 Children & citizens media products and Siân Astley (EUROFIR), Ixai Salvo (Eurofish International Organisation), Themis Altintzoglou (NOFIMA), Karl Presser and Malwina Ciesla (Premotec), Christine Absil and Michelle Boonstra (Clupea) and Tim Huntington and Tracy Murai (Poseidon) participated.

Figure 1: VeriFish partner meeting in Crete, March 2025. The first requirements gathering session for the media products was organised in that remit, on March 20th.

Requirements were gathered using an online board, FigJam, and compiled collaboratively. The online tool was set up with boards to brainstorm on:

- Target audience - high level categories as defined by VeriFish (see chapter 4)
- Target audience - specific examples from the above mentioned categories
- Regional approach
- Which VeriFish indicators (See D2.1, D2.2) to consider, and which attributes
- What to retrieve from factsheets and implement in the product
- Seafood sustainability: how to play with it
- How to promote the products

Figure 2 Extract of the FigJam board used during the first requirements gathering session in Crete

3. Overview of VeriFish media products

During the requirements gathering workshop the consortium brainstormed about the production of the following media products:

- Posters
- Downloadable calendar
- Flash cards game
- Map of fisheries puzzle
- Board game

For each of them, in addition to the already discussed attributes, there was an effort to answer the following questions:

- What format for the products, Paper + digital
- Branding - VeriFish or white labelled
- Where to access them - website or webapp
- Regional approach

4. Identified target users for the media products

As presented in *D3.1 – Communication, stakeholder engagement plan, including branding guide and promotional material*² stakeholders are interconnected in numerous ways, forming a complex web of connected entities that significantly influence sustainability practices. VeriFish media products target **four stakeholder groups** and will be iteratively developed accordingly using iterative approaches.

As presented in *D3.1 – Communication, stakeholder engagement plan, including branding guide and promotional material*, VeriFish mapped a diverse set of stakeholders interconnected across the seafood value chain, including seafood retailers, consumers and consumer associations, children (via parents and educators), European citizens, fisheries and aquaculture producer organisations, policy stakeholders, funding agencies, and standards and good practice organisations. Within this broader landscape, VeriFish media products specifically target **four stakeholder groups** — seafood retailers, consumers and consumer associations, children, and European citizens — and will be developed accordingly using iterative approaches. The two stakeholder groups European citizens and consumers are largely overlapping but have slightly different focus. The European citizens focus more on European persons having voting rights and influence policy making, while consumers focus more on the persons consuming seafood.

² Barazzetta, F., & Salvo Borda, I. (2024). D3.1 – Communication, stakeholder engagement plan, including branding guide and promotional material (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14383716>

Figure 3: Four stakeholders identified by the VeriFish project which are the target of the media products

According to the preliminary outcomes detailed in *D4.1 Initial recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood*, the four stakeholder types can be grouped into two sub-categories:

- SG1: Seafood Retailers & HoReCa and SG2: Consumers and consumer associations can be named "**Creators**", those who have an interest in designing, marketing and distributing media products and will most likely finance communication materials;
- SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens: those will be the subject of communication campaigns and recipients of the media products, that we will name "**Recipients of the campaigns**".

Each product will be customized according to the target group. Below additional information about the characteristics of each of these four stakeholder types are provided, linked with the purpose of designing media products suitable for them.

4.1. SG1: Seafood Retailers & HoReCa

Why: Providing seafood retailers and HoReCa (Hotels, Restaurants and Cafes) professionals with clear, accessible information, and ways to display it, on the environmental and nutritional value of aquatic foods can help them inform their customers' choices and potentially benefit their business. Providing verifiable sustainability and nutrition information helps Seafood Retailers & HoReCa differentiate their business competitively, build brand trust, meet evolving regulatory requirements, and align with consumer demand trends for sustainable food, plus helping them showcase those sustainability credentials that are becoming a market expectation in Europe (e.g., ESG trends, eco-labelling).

Stakeholder Group	Key Topics	Description
SG1: Seafood Retailers & HoReCa	Sustainable Fishing Practices	Promote and source seafood from sustainable sources
	Regulatory Compliance	Ensuring adherence to sustainability standards and regulations.
	Industry Collaboration	Encouraging partnerships with fisheries and aquaculture producers to ensure a steady supply of sustainable seafood.
	Advocacy for Supportive Policies	Working together to advocate for policies that support sustainable fishing and aquaculture practices.
	Training Opportunities	Providing staff with education and training on sustainable seafood practices.

4.2. SG2: Consumers and consumer associations

Why: Help raise awareness about the health benefits, nutritional values, and sustainability of aquatic foods, supporting informed consumer choices and building confidence that choices contribute to the well-being (humans) and health of the planet. Better information empowers consumers to reward sustainable practices through their purchasing power, creating market pressure for sustainable production. The European Union is prioritizing consumer rights to transparent information about food, particularly through initiatives like the Farm to Fork Strategy³. This focus aims to empower consumers to make informed choices about their food, promoting healthy and sustainable diets

Stakeholder Group	Key Topics	Description
SG2: Consumers and Consumer Associations	Sustainable Fishing Practices	Educating consumers on the importance of choosing seafood from sustainable sources.
	Health Benefits	Highlighting the nutritional and health benefits of consuming sustainable seafood.
	Transparency and Trust	Providing clear and verifiable information about the sustainability of seafood products.
	Advocacy for Better Labelling	Promoting better labelling and transparency in seafood sourcing.
	Community Engagement	Encouraging community involvement and participation in sustainable seafood initiatives.

³ https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en

4.3. SG3: Children via parents and educators

Why: Use social media, influencers, and engaging 'understanding game' tools to inform audiences—especially young people—about the sustainability aspects of seafood, helping to shape future mindsets and encourage sustainable production and consumption habits. Receiving correct and complete information creates lasting consumption patterns on children, as they grow up with sustainable seafood awareness and therefore are more likely to adopt sustainable consumption habits into adulthood. Parents and educators also can play a multiplier factor by influencing relatives and family networks. This is the case of many seafood campaigns (like the Norwegian Seafood Council) trying to reach the "buyers" of the families, i.e. the parents who are (very often) the ones to decide the purchase of the family and thus have a massive impact on the eating habits of their children. By combining accurate, reliable information with gamified and storytelling approaches, VeriFish aims at making complex issues like sustainability, accessible and memorable, reinforcing long-term behavioural change.

Stakeholder Group	Key Topics	Description
SG3: Children via Parents and Educators	Educational Programs	Developing educational content and programs about sustainable seafood.
	Health and Nutrition	Teaching children about the health benefits of consuming seafood.
	Interactive Learning	Creating interactive and engaging content to make learning about seafood fun and memorable.
	Parental Involvement	Involving parents in educational activities to reinforce learning at home.
	Community and School Events	Organizing events that promote sustainable seafood practices within the community and schools.

4.4. SG4: European Citizens

Why: Citizens are bombarded with too much information, sometimes confusing and sometimes contradictory, about seafood, health, and sustainability. At the same time, European citizens are key drivers for political and market change, and their informed choices influence not only markets but policy demands too. Providing verified, holistic, and multilingual information on aquatic food production and consumption to support responsible, informed decisions around sustainability, biodiversity, seasonality, nutrition, and health is of great value to empower citizens to make choices.

Stakeholder Group	Key Topics	Description
European Citizens	Sustainable Seafood Awareness	Raising awareness about the importance of sustainable seafood practices.
	Health Benefits	Highlighting the health benefits of consuming sustainably sourced seafood.

have been designed from a marketing and graphical perspective, as well as some considerations on how aspects related to sustainability or environmental awareness have been addressed.

5.1. Examples of educational materials

5.1.1. Analysed examples

1) **Marine Conservation Society fact files on Biodiversity, Ecosystems Services, Ocean Threats, Sustainable Fishing, Climate Change, PFAS**

Design specifications: A series of fact files in A4 format, downloadable as PDFs, designed with mainly textual descriptions and definitions, supported by a few small images. No branding, just a color code associated with each thematic, and the Marine Conservation Society logo on the bottom of the page. Photo credits provided. Each fact sheet includes definitions and explanations of the key concept of the file, with concrete examples taken from European regions.

General Considerations: There is no reference to the sources of the data and information included in the files. The fact files appear to be only be available in English

2) **Mr GoodFish Seasonal recommendations**

Link: <https://www.mrgoodfish.com/en/especies/>

Design specifications: Archive, database of selected species selected by Mr GoodFish from 20 March to 20 June 2025. The web page shows well designed cards with the common name, plus the scientific one, together with a representative picture of the fish. If the card is pointed, the “Learn More” action is specified. There is a search bar to filter the research by:

- Coastline (Brittany/ Atlantic Brittany/ Atlantic; Channel/ North Sea; French Overseas; Mediterranean Sea)
- Origin (Farmed; Wild)
- Seafood Name - only the “All seafood” filter is available.

General Considerations: The database on the Mr GoodFish website is regularly updated to reflect the seasonal availability of the listed species. The filter feature allows users to easily refine their search, and selecting the origin and coastline provides more detailed information on the back of the card when it is pointed at.

4.1) **Mr GoodFish seasonal recommendations Poster**

Link:

<https://www.mrgoodfish.com/en/mr-goodfish/mr-goodfish-recommendations-for-aquaculture-2/recom-mandations-de-la-saison/>

Design Specifications: Poster document style with illustrations. The document outlines the recommendations from December 21, 2024 to March 19, 2025. It is made of 3 different boxes, which differentiate the fisheries species based on the zone (Atlantic Nord- Est, 27 species identified; North Sea, 7 species identified; Atlantic Ocean, 13 species identified; Mediterranean Sea, 35 species identified). There is a QRCode at the bottom to access the Mr GoodFish web application.

General Considerations: The poster is well structured, each box shows the common species and their specifications- such as the scientific name and the dimension- with for each zone described and a representative image. There is also an asterisk (*) to clarify that some of the mentioned species are not scientifically evaluated.

Figure 5: Mr GoodFish recommendations for aquaculture - seasonal recommendations poster

3) [Blue Mission Med Our Blue Treasure Book](https://bluemissionmed.eu/the-blue-mission-med-book-for-kids-officially-launched-at-eu-ocean-days/)

Link:

<https://bluemissionmed.eu/the-blue-mission-med-book-for-kids-officially-launched-at-eu-ocean-days/>

Design specifications: Targeted at children aged 6 to 10, the book simplifies complex environmental concepts into colorful, interactive content. There are collected challenges/ games oriented to raise awareness about the impact of daily actions on the health of our ocean and waters, and the reciprocal effect of water well-being on our lives. encourages active participation through games, challenges, and activities, where children can use stickers to complete information. It's mentioned that every aspect of the book was scientifically and pedagogically validated by the BlueMissionMed consortium, ensuring accuracy and educational value.

General Considerations: The book is well structured, the target audience can gain a deeper understanding of how their actions can influence the ocean and waters. The book is available both on printed copies into multiple languages (English, Italian, Greek, Spanish, Dutch, Maltese, Turkish, French, and Arabic) and digital versions, allowing children to interact with content by dragging and dropping stickers, making the learning process both fun and informative.

Figure 6: The BlueMissionMed children's book "Our Blue Treasure"

4) Bloom Association booklet (French edition)

Link:

https://bloomassociation.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Livret_Ocean_Climat_A5_12p_2021_sans_t

[raits_coupe.pdf?_gl=1*pgl457*_gcl_au*NjE4NDgyMDU0LjE3NDQxMjc4MDc.*_ga*Njg2Mzc1MzlxLjE3NDQxMjc4MDQ.*_ga_1M79DPKJQ7*MTc0NDE0MzgZNC4yLjEuMTc0NDE0MzkwMC41Ni4wLjA.](#)

Design specifications: Report/brief document style booklet with illustrations. There is mainly text and it is subdivided into 8 chapters about climate change impacts, sea level, extreme climate phenomena, ocean acidification, and social and economic impacts. Branding aligned with the DeepSea Conservation Coalition logo, varied layout with highlights, different headings and fonts, pictures and photos. Link at the bottom to learn more, but not clickable.

General Considerations: Sources of scientific information are quoted as footnotes. Multiple logos are included, one of the Bloom Association and another one from the DeepSea Conservation Coalition, suggesting a partnership. The nice message in the header facilitates immediate understanding of the scope of the booklet (“Océan / climat: le petit guide qui évite de dire de grosses bêtises” = The small guide to avoid saying the wrong thing).

5) [UNESCO Annual Agenda - “Educazione all’oceano per tutti - Kit pratico” \(italian version\)](#)

Link: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373637>

Design specifications: Booklet/ Report guide with representative pictures and tables. There is mainly text and it is subdivided into 3 chapters about the education of the ocean, its history and its future; the essential principles of the Ocean Education, the explanation; and the "current" to be followed, as a guide to construct a partnership in the current ocean governance with some success stories. Branding aligned with the UNESCO logo. Link at the bottom to learn more, but not clickable.

General Considerations: Material published in the UNESCO Doc Digital Library, which is a useful database to consider for dissemination, since this publication is available in Open Access, license with Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 IGO (CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/igo/>). The manual is well-structured and designed to appeal to a broad and diverse audience, including scientists, educators, and students. It encourages individuals to take greater personal responsibility for the ocean, inspiring them to act as engaged citizens. Moreover, it promotes collaboration and networking, the sharing of ideas and experiences, and the development of innovative approaches and initiatives in support of Ocean Literacy.

5.2. Games

There are many different kinds of games that tackle animals, their behaviours and environmental sustainability. From the more complex ones, such as *Ark Nova* and its complex management structures, to simple traditional games that are based on pairing cards, many different examples can be used to visualize and communicate about seafood sustainability and marine life. Games like *Finspan* (a fishy version of *Wingspan*), help to understand the different species of fishes and their behaviours, while the famous game *Sardines*⁴ gives a funny introduction to children on what fishes are.

⁴ s: <https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/27071/sardines>

5.2.1. Driving examples

In the following section, we are going to analyse two examples that will guide future development of games.

1) Exploding Kitten

Link: <https://www.explodingkittens.com/>

Rules of the game: Exploding Kittens is a card game where players try to avoid drawing an "Exploding Kitten" card, which eliminates them from the game. Players take turns drawing cards from a deck until someone draws an Exploding Kitten. They can use "Defuse" cards to save themselves from exploding or other cards to influence the game. The last player remaining wins. For players aged 6 and up.

Design specifications: Exploding Kittens features whimsical, absurd cat illustrations by The Oatmeal, paired with a bright and humorous art style. The game uses clear iconography and color coding to ensure quick and easy card recognition.

Branding: The game comes in a compact, sturdy box featuring bold, comic-style artwork that reflects its brand identity of irreverent humor and a viral internet tone. Iconic visuals like the exploding kitten and sarcastic text reinforce its playful, distinctive style.

Educational approach: Exploding Kittens promotes informal learning by encouraging strategic thinking, social interaction, emotional regulation, and pattern recognition. Players must anticipate opponents' moves, manage risk, and adapt strategies in real time. The game also fosters group dynamics, turn-taking, and humor-driven engagement, making it a playful tool for developing cognitive and social-emotional skills.

2) [Nature challenge game](#) (by Bioviva Foundation)

Link: <https://www.bioviva.com/en/collections/4-nature-challenge>

Figure 7: example of Nature Challenge cards game with aquatic animals

Rules of the game: Each player receives an equal number of animal cards. On their turn, the first player chooses one characteristic from their top card (e.g., weight, lifespan, speed) and challenges the others. All players reveal the same stat from their top card, and the one with the highest value wins the round and collects the cards. If a player draws an endangered species card, special rules apply that can influence the round. The game continues until one player collects all the cards.

Design specifications: The game features a compact, pocket-sized card deck designed for portability and convenience. Each card is made with a durable, glossy finish to withstand frequent handling. Cards include detailed information such as the animal's name, a high-quality photograph, habitat details, IUCN conservation status, and key statistics like size, speed, and longevity. The layout is clear and consistent, with intuitive icons and data visualizations that make comparing animals easy and engaging.

Branding: Défis Nature is a well-known educational card game series by the French publisher Bioviva, recognized for eco-friendly production and nature-themed content. The branding emphasizes environmental awareness and curiosity, with a colorful, nature-inspired design and real animal

photography. The logo and game style are consistent across the Défis Nature product line, building a strong, recognizable identity.

Educational approach: The game supports learning through play by teaching players about biodiversity, animal traits, and conservation. Children become familiar with scientific terms and ecological concepts (like endangered species and habitats) while comparing real-world data. It also encourages critical thinking, memory skills, and respectful competition. The game is designed to be both fun and informative, sparking curiosity about wildlife and environmental issues.

5.2.2. Other analysed examples

Below additional examples are analysed. They have been included due to their relation with the topic (fishery, ocean literacy) or the provider being a renown and reliable institute / organisation (WWF, OGS, The Ocean Cleanup)

3) Fischmarkt (Clementoni)

Link: <https://boardgamegeek.com/boardgame/22233/fischmarkt>

Rules of the game: Players bid secretly on boats to collect fish cards, aiming to match fish types shown on hidden demand cards. After the auction, players negotiate trades to get the fish they need. Price cards are revealed to determine how much each player earns. Unused fish can be frozen (with limited space). Profits are calculated, and players move on the score track. The game lasts 4 rounds, with increasing fish per boat in later rounds.

Design specifications: includes an auction board, individual player boards, fish cards (with different fish types: red, grey, herring, lobster), demand cards, price cards, player screens, ice cube tokens, money, and scoring markers. Card design is functional and color-coded. Fish are depicted realistically on cards, while boards are more cartoon-like.

Branding: The game does not prominently showcase the brand's logo within the components described. There is no mention of logo placement on boards, cards, or packaging in the text, indicating that branding is likely minimal or subtle, possibly limited to the box or rulebook.

Educational approach: Teaches strategic planning, resource and money management, market evaluation, and negotiation. Players learn to adapt to shifting supply and demand and must communicate and make deals effectively. Visual cues and simple mechanics help new players quickly understand core concepts.

4) [RESPONSEABLE](#) ([ResponSEable Horizon2020 project](#) on Ocean Literacy)

Link: <https://responseable.acteon-environment.eu/>

Rules of the game: The game unfolds through five *Stories* set in an archipelago. The goal is to complete all stages by answering quizzes related to ocean health and its value chain. Along the way, players can

earn points and take breaks with mini-games. After completing all challenges, players can take a selfie that appears on the game's homepage as a symbol of their commitment to protecting the ocean.

Design specifications: It is a free, ad-free interactive mobile app that collects no personal data. Available for Android and iOS devices.

Branding: The game is part of the ResponSEAbLe project, funded by the European Union under the Horizon2020 programme. The project's branding and logo appear within the app and related materials. It was developed by [CSP innovazione nelle ICT](#) in collaboration with European partners.

Educational approach: Through quizzes, stories, and mini-games, players learn about marine pollution, eutrophication, coastal changes, and human impact on marine ecosystems. The game supports *ocean literacy*, making complex environmental topics engaging and accessible. The [ResponSEAbLe Horizon2020 project](#) developed many other media products for citizens ([see list here](#)) and other stakeholders which will be further investigated.

5) [Il memory del mare](#) (Fantavolando - Italian version)

Link: <https://fantavolando.it/attivita-per-estate-il-memory-del-mare/>

Rules of the game: We place the tiles face down on the table to create three rows of four tiles each. We invite one child at a time to turn over two tiles and name the animals depicted. If the animals match, the child takes the two tiles and may choose two more. Otherwise, the turn passes to the next child. At the end, each child counts the tiles they have collected to see who has won. Variations of the game can be introduced based on the children's age. For example, they can be asked to name the color of the animal, its characteristics, and so on.

Design specifications: White A4 card, colored A4 sheets, markers or crayons, glue, scissors.

Branding: the logo is present on the tiles, positioned in the top left corner.

Educational approach: The game focuses on developing perceptual skills through visual challenges, pattern recognition, and observation tasks related to marine environments. These activities help players improve attention to detail, memory, and visual discrimination while learning about ocean health and human impact, making complex ecological topics more accessible and engaging.

6) [Il gambero invisibile](#) (ERSAF - Regione Lombardia - Italian version)

Link: <https://gamberodifiume.ersaflombardia.it/>

Rules of the game: this game is centered around the Italian river crayfish, and there are 8+1 missions to complete, each with its own theme, such as Pollution, Marine waste, Fishing nets, Predators, and some more. In each mission, the player must remove harmful elements from the crayfish's various habitats.

Design specifications: It is a free, educational, and entertaining web app.

Branding: The logos of the organizations are displayed in the top right corner of the screen, leaving the main space for the game logo.

Educational approach: Users can see how they could help the river crayfish lead a better life, thanks to the explanations that appear on the screen at the end of each mission.

7) [Il gioco del mare](https://oneplanetschool.wwf.it/gioca-e-scopri/il-gioco-del-mare) (WWF - italian version)

Link: <https://oneplanetschool.wwf.it/gioca-e-scopri/il-gioco-del-mare>

Rules of the game: The game consists of identifying 5 harmful elements for the Mediterranean environment. After selecting them, a detailed page appears with in-depth information on various topics related to the Mediterranean.

Branding: WWF logo is displayed on the top of the screen

Design specifications: It is a free online game

Educational approach: After finishing the game, a screen appears with 11 icons representing 11 different topics. By clicking on each one, an explanation about the selected topic is displayed, along with external links to further deepen knowledge.

8) [Fish'n Ships](https://www.fishnships.it/) (Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, project funded by the Interreg Italia-Croazia FAIRSEA programme, the Interreg Italia-Croazia TECHERA programme and the Regione Autonoma Friuli Venezia Giulia)

Link: <https://www.fishnships.it/>

Rules of the game: Fish n' Ships is a card game that educates players about marine ecosystems and sustainable fishing. It features 36 species from the Adriatic Sea, categorized by trophic levels (producers, primary, secondary, and tertiary consumers). Players first build a balanced marine ecosystem, then use fishing cards to catch species, each with environmental impacts. Special cards introduce environmental issues, both positive (Marine Protected Areas, Innovation) and negative (Climate Change, Illegal Fishing). Scores are earned based on species, fishing systems, and trophies. There are 7 types of cards, each characterized by a different color.

Branding: The game does not prominently showcase the brand's logo within the components described. There is no mention of logo placement on boards or cards, indicating that branding is likely minimal.

Design specifications: It is an online card game

Educational approach: The game introduces trophic levels through colored cards, illustrating the ecological pyramid and marine food web sustainability. Malus cards highlight harmful events like climate change and illegal fishing, while bonus cards promote sustainability practices such as marine protected areas. The scoring system reinforces the importance of fishing without disrupting the ecosystem's balance.

9) [Mission Ocean](#) (Adventerra Games in collaboration with The Ocean Cleanup)

Link: <https://adventerragames.com/it/shop/mission-ocean-gioco-da-tavolo/>

Rules of the game: Players take turns clockwise, starting with the youngest. On their turn, a player rolls two dice: the white die triggers a special action, and the blue die determines movement (1–4 sea zones). Players navigate the board to rescue their animal by reaching it and removing a piece of plastic, then transporting the plastic to the rescue ship. If movement points exactly match the steps needed to reach the animal, the player gets an extra turn. The first player to free their animal and bring all plastic to the ship wins.

Branding: The game does not prominently showcase the brand's logo within the components described. There is no mention of logo placement on boards, cards, or packaging in the text, indicating that branding is likely minimal or subtle, possibly limited to the box or rulebook.

Design specifications: The Ocean Cleanup's boat, game board, 4 marine animal tokens, 24 waste tokens, 2 wooden dice, 4 large wooden discs.

Educational approach: Inside the box, there is an educational ecological guide that introduces children to the challenges of plastic pollution and shows them how they can help solve the problem.

5.3. Puzzles

Existing example: [Puzzle "Observation of the world"](#)

Link: <https://www.cittadelsole.it/ita/prodotto/puzzle-200-pezzi-osservazione-del-mondo>

Design specifications: A 200-piece puzzle, a poster and a booklet to learn the names of the tourist places on the map. A puzzle and an observation game: the pieces of the puzzle must be found in the booklet. It contains a poster the size of the puzzle that serves as a model. The materials are full of illustrations and descriptions for each item included.

General Considerations: The game includes a 200-piece puzzle, a poster and a booklet. Stimulates children's tourist curiosity and it engages well with the target audience thanks to its design, colors and animated illustrations. A quality puzzle made of FSC certified paper to do and redo as many times as you like in a colorful box, easy to store. Made in Europe.

Figure 8: Puzzle 200 pieces. Observation of the world

5.4. High-level outcomes and considerations

The analysis of the media products above reveals a diverse and dynamic landscape of tools developed by public institutions, EU-funded projects, and NGOs. The analysed materials are tailored to early education (to form sustainable habits) and public awareness (providing clear information for adult citizens) – therefore targeting children, young students, families, and the general public with basic knowledge. Materials adopt a variety of formats – from fact sheets and posters to interactive games and comprehensive guidebooks. Many of the most impactful resources, especially those designed for children and families, employ gamification and play-based learning strategies, which promote engagement and curiosity towards environmental themes.

One of the persistent limitations across these materials is linguistic accessibility. While some tools, particularly books and board games, are available in multiple EU languages, a large number remain monolingual – often in English or French, thereby limiting their reach and inclusivity across Europe’s linguistically diverse population.

Some recommendations that VeriFish will implement to tackle linguistic issues include i) **prioritise multilingual versions** at least in the EU languages covered by the consortium – English, French, Spanish, Danish, Italian, Polish, Greek, Norwegian; ii) **consider visual communication**, such as infographics and icons, to reduce language dependency.

Another recurrent issue is the **lack of transparency in sourcing information**. Most materials do not provide clear references, relying instead on the reputations of the producing organisations (e.g., UNESCO, WWF, OGS). While this institutional credibility provides a level of trust, materials such as the *Bloom Association booklet* demonstrate that referencing sources – scientific articles, official statistics, and institutional research – can significantly enhance communication integrity.

The *BlueMissionMed* book stands out in this regard, as its development process spanned over a year and involved deep scientific research, pedagogical structuring, narrative crafting, and illustration, with every element validated by the consortium to ensure accuracy and relevance, but evidence of this approach is not included in the book itself (while available by browsing online). Similarly, the Mr. GoodFish programme offers a strong example of expert collaboration. Its aquaculture species recommendations are established by a multidisciplinary committee involving scientists (from institutions such as IFREMER, INRA, CIRAD), aquaculture producers, inter-branch organisations like CIPA, food producers, institutional representatives, retailers (METRO, TRANSGOURMET, SEAFOOD), consumer associations (CLCV), and members of its own national coordination. Highlighting this multi-stakeholder approach reinforces the robustness and credibility of the recommendations and it would be recommended to introduce an acknowledgement about clear and transparent referencing of sources and the integration of expert collaboration in all materials developed.

6. Preliminary requirements

6.1. Species considered for the media products

The media products to be designed will address sustainability challenges by relying on verifiable information and data sources, as presented in the VeriFish indicator framework (*D2.1, D2.2, D2.4*). To make the materials appealing for the target audiences, some of the media products will focus on some specific species, offering real life examples that seafood retailers and HoReCa representatives, consumers and consumer associations, parents and educators recognise in their everyday lives.

Designed and aimed to be entertaining, the media products will also rely on scientifically accurate data. In order to identify a number of species to use in the design of the media products, the most consumed species in the EU-27 countries according to the EU FISH MARKET 2024 report⁵ have been analysed:

⁵The EU Fish Market 2024 edition https://eumofa.eu/documents/20124/145239/EFM2024_EN.pdf Chapter 3.1 Overview for total fishery and, aquaculture products, page 40.

Table 1: Apparent consumption of top-15 most consumed products (2022). Source: EUMOFA, based on EUROSTAT.

TABLE 10
APPARENT CONSUMPTION
OF TOP-15 MOST
CONSUMED PRODUCTS
(2022)

Source: EUMOFA, based on EUROSTAT (online data codes: [fish_ca_main](#), [fish_aq2a](#) and [DS-045409](#)) and FAO data. Details on the sources and on the methodological approach used for assessing the production method of imports and exports and the destination use of catches can be found in the Methodological background.

Products	Per capita consumption (kg, LWE)	Consumption evolution 2022/2021	% wild	% farmed
Tuna	2,96	+4%	99,2%	0,8%
Salmon	2,51	-3%	5,7%	94,3%
Shrimps	1,68	+4%	43,0%	57,0%
Alaska pollock	1,67	-1%	100%	0%
Cod	1,63	-7%	99,9%	0,1%
Mussel	1,21	-3%	6,4%	93,6%
Hake	1,03	+1%	100%	0%
Herring	0,87	-14%	100%	0%
Squid	0,73	+2%	100%	0%
Surimi	0,60	-3%	100%	0%
Sardine	0,55	+2%	100%	0%
Mackerel	0,54	+3%	100%	0%
Trout	0,46	-6%	0,7%	99,3%
Scallop	0,37	+36%	80,7%	19,3%
Saithe (=Coalfish)	0,37	+4%	100%	0%
Other products	6,32	-1%	71,5%	28,5%
Total	23,51	-1%	29,0%	71,0%

As Verifish needs to address several objectives, further considerations were made in order to come up with species variety to reflect these different objectives. Namely:

- Sustainability aspects can be clearly explained with the species (invasive species, cephalopods)
- The species group has a very high nutritional value in relation to the environmental footprint (small pelagics, bivalves)
- The species is consumed in high volumes in the EU and has both sustainable and less sustainable choices (salmon and tunas)
- The species are important in EU aquaculture (trout, seabass and seabream)
- The species are caught in the EU and can be promoted as alternative for imported products (whitefish: saithe, hake, whiting, shrimps: Northern shrimp *Pandalus borealis*)
- The species is less known but is very responsibly farmed (carp, arctic char).
- The species group is relevant for European fisheries but some species are less well known (flatfishes)

Considering all the above, the VeriFish consortium decided to rely on the following 25 species organised into 10 categories, which will be referred to, to design the media products:

Categories	Species
1. Bivalves	1. Mussels - <i>Mytilus edulis</i> , <i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> 2. Oysters – various 3. Scallop – <i>Pecten Maximus</i> (farmed) * 4. Cockle - <i>Cerastoderma edule</i> , or Japanese carpet shells <i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i> ** *Scallops can also be dredged
2. Crustaceans	5. Northern prawn - <i>Pandalus borealis</i> 6. American swamp crayfish - <i>Procambarus clarkii</i> ** 7. Blue swimming crab - <i>Callinectes sapidus</i> ** ** invasive species
3. Flatfish	8. Plaice – <i>Pleuronectes platessa</i> 9. Dab – <i>Limanda limanda</i> 10. Flounder <i>Platichthys flesus</i>
4. Whitefish	11. Whiting - <i>Merlangius merlangus</i> 12. Hake - <i>Merluccius merluccius</i> 13. Saithe - <i>Pollachius virens</i>
5. Small pelagics ⁶	14. Herring <i>Clupea harengus</i> 15. Sardines <i>Sardina pilchardus</i>
6. Freshwater	16. Carp - <i>Cyprinus carpio</i> 17. Trout - <i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i> 18. Arctic char - <i>Salvelinus alpinus</i>
7. Salmon	19. Atlantic salmon <i>Salmo salar</i> (aquaculture: ASC) 20. Pacific salmon (wild capture: various species MSC)
8. Popular in Mediterranean aquaculture	21. Seabream – <i>Sparus aurata</i> (aquaculture: ASC) 22. Seabass - <i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i> (aquaculture ASC)
9. Tunas	23. Albacore – <i>Thunnus alalunga</i> (MSC) 24. Skipjack – <i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i> (MSC) 25. Yellowfin - <i>Thunnus albacares</i> (MSC)

⁶ Unfortunately Atlantic mackerel is on the way to being seriously overfished so for now it is better not to use it in recipes. See <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2025/apr/09/mackerel-stocks-near-breaking-point-because-of-overfishing-say-experts>

Categories	Species
10. Cephalopods	26. Common octopus <i>Octopus vulgaris</i> 27. European Squid <i>Loligo vulgaris</i>

6.2. Acknowledgement of VeriFish data sources

As reported in *D4.1 Initial recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood*, key prerequisites for any of the recommended communication strategies to be effective and of relevance is use of verifiable and reliable information. Acknowledgement of data sources will be included in each of the media products, including also appropriate temporal and spatial scale. It will be included in the instructions, in the package or in the media product text itself.

6.3. Recommendations from D4.1

As reported in *D4.1 Initial recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood*, some attributes for seafood are either required by law and/or desirable to communicate, regardless of consumer type. Some examples include the required nutritional declaration on prepacked food, common organisation of the market in fishery and aquaculture products, and the use of catch certificates to show that the catch was acquired in compliance with applicable laws and regulations. Whenever any of the media products to be designed refers to a species associated with an attribute required by law, or desirable to communicate, these attributes / declarations will be included in the media products (instructions, package or where else appropriate).

6.4. Posters

Format	Branding	How to access	Licence	Regional approach
Virtual printable	VeriFish label White label	Link from the VeriFish website Link from the VeriFish Mobile App Available at distributing stakeholders' places	CC-BY-4	Yes - depend on type of poster

Format: Posters will be conceived as large infographics, available as downloads and printable files, as well as accessible online, as virtual posters. **Printable posters** will be in one or more typical poster formats - A0 (vertical, 118x84 cm), A1 (horizontal 60x84 cm) or A2 (vertical, 42x60cm). They can also be bigger, like geographical maps (140x100 cm). **Digital posters** will be electronic displays featuring the

same content but more dynamic and interactive, sized for typical screen formats (e.g., 16:9 widescreen). They will include links to VeriFish and other online resources.

Branding: Versions will be designed in a way that **additional logos and icons can be added**, provided by users, as desired. Acknowledgement of the EC funding and the logo of the VeriFish project will be displayed at the bottom.

Accessibility: Printable posters will be uploaded on Zenodo and signposted from the VeriFish website and web-app. Users who want to download and print the posters will be able to do so, in different formats (.pdf, .svg, others) and sizes. Downloads will be tracked via the number of downloads from Zenodo.

For those who want to **co-brand posters** with different logos / icons, a specific version will be released, to be customized by the entity or by the VeriFish consortium (Trust-IT) upon specific request, in case the entity does not have in-house capacity (this option will be offered until April 2026). Instructions for in-house customisation will be provided, too. For posters that need to be co-branded, users will have to notify the VeriFish consortium and acknowledge the VeriFish project about the usage via a photo on social media, if possible, and provide a few details about purpose and outcomes of the use (where it was showcased, in which occasion, to whom, etc..) via a follow-up form.

Licence: Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Regional Approach: Posters might have a regional (geographical) approach, according to the content, the species and the topic addressed, as further detailed below.

6.4.1. How to address sustainability: poster topics

The posters described below will be produced.

1) Posters about the scientific names of fisheries

Purpose: Very often people refer to seafood using the incorrect name for a given species. The purpose of this poster is to explain the concepts of scientific and common names, and genus, and the importance of accurate species identification. Provide a “dictionary-like” list of species names referring back to scientific names, to support user identification in their language or in another.

Target groups:

- Creators: SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens

Number of posters: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
<p>A poster listing scientific unique names of all species available in the VeriFish knowledge base, by alphabetical order, combined with the genus of the species and the common names in English, Danish, Greek, Italian, Norwegian, Polish, Spanish, possibly French in collaboration with MrGoodFish partners.</p> <p>2 versions will be released: 1) a multi-language poster and 2) a country-based version with only common names in 7 languages covered by the consortium.</p>	All	GRSF, OpenAPI

2) Posters about ecological impact of different gear types

Purpose: Improve understanding of the potential environmental impacts associated with capture fisheries, with a focus on gear-specific ecological considerations such as biology, habitat interactions, gear-related effects, and gear loss. For example, why are certain species caught using certain gear types due to their life cycles, feeding and place where they live.

Target groups:

- Creators: SG1: SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens

Number of posters: 7 gear type per poster using categories as provided by the FAO Fishing Gear type Fact Sheets⁷:

1. Trawl and dredging
2. Hooks and lines
3. Gillnets and entangling nets
4. Traps and pots
5. Lift nets
6. Seine nets
7. Miscellaneous Gears

⁷ Search technology factsheets <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/geartype>

Figure 9: List of Fishing Gear types by picture as included in the FAO Fact Sheets

Language versions: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
<p>Infographic combining in one unique poster information about the potential environmental impact related to the use of a given gear to different species caught using this method. The poster can demonstrate how the different gear types are used in different geographies to capture lots of different species. The poster will combine textual and quantitative / data information with visuals and catchy sentences focusing on Tier 1 data from the capture fishery indicators, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● impact of that gear type on marine ecosystems ● concept of "bycatch" and examples of amount of discard typical for gear type and landed catch ● gear used to fish, considered per seabed type proxy, and the impact of gear loss <p>Different posters can be designed, each one focusing on one of the species identified in chapter 6.1. Information about fishers livelihoods can be added as info boxes, referred to each species (e.g. short trips vs. long trips for the different gears e.g. purse seine might be multi day whereas pots/traps usually small scale day trips.)</p>	<p>Capture fisheries environmental indicators on Habitat impact, Trophic effects, Bycatch, ETP impact, Gear loss</p>	<p>FAO gear type⁸, GRSF, EMODnet biology, SeaAroundUs, EMODnet Biology, BMIS, IUCN, EUNIS</p>

3) Poster on stock status and FAO areas for capture fishes

⁸ <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/geartype>

Purpose: Explain the concept of fish stock. Raise awareness about the importance of recognising the location where fish are caught (ocean, lake, or river). Simplify understanding of oceanic catch areas categorised into FAO regions worldwide and further divided into smaller GFCM regions (General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean), as reported on products on the market.

Target groups:

- Creators: SG1: SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens

Number of posters: 1

Language versions: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
1 poster will be designed as a planisphere of ocean and inland seas with indication of the corresponding FAO regions and GFCM regions. Informative boxes will provide definitions of catch areas, species stock and governance (e.g. IUU fish or corruption). The 16 species identified (see chapter 5.1) will be positioned on the planisphere, introducing FAO illustrations of the species and the illustrations coming from Wikimedia, scaled according to the level of the stock (for instance, from 1 fish to 5).	Capture fisheries environmental indicators on stock status	GRSF, Wikimedia API, FishBase, SeaLifeBase

4) Poster on responsible aquaculture by technology / production system

Purpose: Provide a comprehensive overview of the aquaculture production cycle for the two identified aquaculture species (rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss* and mussels, *Mytilus* spp.), and how a sustainable production cycle should be.

Target groups:

- Creators: SG1: SG1: Seafood Retailers & HoReCa, SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens

Number of posters: 1

Language versions: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
The poster will present in an infographic format all the attributes related to aquaculture described in the VeriFish indicator framework (D2.2). An aquaculture production cycle for the farmed species identified (Freshwater species, salmon and Species that are popular in Mediterranean aquaculture, as detailed in par. 5.1) will be designed, including informative boxes dedicated to the species cultivated, presented at genus level (+ common names), feeding mechanisms, suggested stocking density, production systems, environment of cultivation (marine, brackish or fresh waters) and alien status (endemic or not in which regions of Europe). Nutritional value add can also be added as info boxes, referred to each species .	Aquaculture indicators (all)	Fair-Fish, EUNIS, EU MSFD, IUCN, EMODnet Biology, OpenAPI

5) Poster on representation of nutrition facts

Purpose: Appeal to health-conscious consumers across various demographics, fostering a connection between sustainability and personal health. Emphasize the health benefits associated with sustainable seafood consumption, such as the presence of omega-3 fatty acids and their role in preventing chronic diseases. Highlights aspects such as if a product type is in need of preparation, we can provide healthy recipes.

Target groups:

- Creators: SG1: Seafood Retailers & HoReCa, SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens

Number of posters: 1

Language versions: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
A poster will be designed as an infographic explaining how to approach nutritional aspects in seafood. The difference between raw products versus cooked and processed products will be explained with some examples using the species selected in par. 5.1, with visual representation of nutrition facts, health claims, low on fat (e.g. high protein, low carbon). The concept of NUTRISCORE will also be explained. Suggestions on seafood less	Nutritional composition data, including macro and micronutrients, were compiled for over 70 fish	FCDBs via EuroFIR's FoodEXplorer tool, possibly FCDBs from other databases

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
familiar to European citizens, but less at risks as well as low trophic value species will be presented. The media types that fit this type of promotion could be ideal for social media (SoMe), product pages, and web site posters from the producer.	species from 39 food composition databases	such as AnFood/BioFoodComp, FishNutrients, uFish, SeaFoodData, AFCD

6.5. Calendar

Format	Branding	How to access	Licence	Regional approach
Virtual Printable	VeriFish label White label	Link from the VeriFish website Link from the VeriFish web-app Available at distributing stakeholders' places	CC-BY-4	No

Format: 12-months calendar will be designed as a printable, downloadable version in two different sizes, vertical for printing and widescreen format to be accessible online. **Printable posters** will be designed in A2 (vertical, 42x60cm). **Digital posters** will be electronic displays featuring the same content but more dynamic and interactive, sized for typical screen formats, typically 16:9 widescreen. They will include links to VeriFish and other online resources. Calendars will be structured in 12 sheets, plus cover and back

Branding: Calendars will be designed such that **additional logos and icons can be added**. Acknowledgement of the EC funding and the logo of the VeriFish project will be displayed at the bottom.

Accessibility: Printable calendars will be uploaded on Zenodo and signposted from the VeriFish website and web-app. Users who simply want to download and print the posters will be able to do so, in different formats (.pdf, .svg, others) and sizes. Downloads will be tracked via the number of downloads from Zenodo.

For those who want to **co-brand the calendars** with different logos / icons, a specific version will be released, to be customized by the entity or by the VeriFish consortium (Trust-IT) upon specific, in case the entity does not have in-house capacity to do so (this option will be offered until April 2026).

Instructions for in-house customisation will be provided, too. For calendars that need to be co-branded, users will have to notify the VeriFish consortium and acknowledge the VeriFish project about the usage.

Licence: Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Regional Approach: No

6.5.1. How to address sustainability with a calendar

Purpose: Give families and other consumers clear, easy-to-understand information about key sustainability aspects. Each of the 12 monthly sheets will focus on one VeriFish pilot species, as listed in par. 5.1, and highlight selected environmental and socio-economic indicators that are most useful for communicating sustainability in both wild-caught and farmed seafood (see D4.1 for more details). An example is presented below. An important aspect to highlight is that we are *not* proposing the calendar for seasonal consumption. Months are not associated with a species suitable for purchase / consumption in that month. Each monthly sheet will retrieve information from the VeriFish species factsheet available from the web-app

Table 2: Example of 12 months distribution of fish sustainability related information

Month	Species	Environmental indicators explained	Socio-economic indicators explained
January	Most consumed doesn't mean sustainable! Introduction to VeriFish list of sustainable species	Stock status	The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species
February	Shellfish	Ecological Impact / ByCatch	Fish populations
March	Crustaceans	Climate Impact	The impacts of fishing on marine ecosystems
April	Flatfish	Governance / Catch limit	What does the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive say
May	Whitefish	Welfare / Capture	Distribution of marine species: WoRMS, EuroBIS and EMODnet
June	Small pelagics	Fishing mortality	Fish stock assessments
July	Freshwater species	Ecological Impact / Gear loss	Health of fish stocks and fishing pressure

Month	Species	Environmental indicators explained	Socio-economic indicators explained
August	Salmon	Ecological Impact / Habitat impact	Food fishes
September	Mediterranean aquaculture	Welfare / Stunning and killing	Endangered, Threatened and Protected Species (ETP Species)
October	Tuna	Governance / ETP mitigation	Fishery Improvement Projects (FIPs)
November	Cephalopods	Governance / IUU	MSC certifications (how they work)
December	Invasive species	Ecological Impact / Trophic effect	ASC certifications (how they work)

Target groups:

- SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators

Number of calendars: 1

Language versions: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
<p>The calendar will address sustainability by introducing each month a different species and providing a description of sustainability aspects including also related details peculiar to that species. Each month a specific “sustainability highlights” box will describe specific environmental and social and economic aspects that should be known by whoever cares about sourcing from fisheries that are assessed to be more sustainable. Nutritional and health attributes related to each given species will be presented, too, together with some cooking suggestions according to the type of products that can be produced out of that species, following on what presented in <i>D4.1 Initial recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood</i> (“In need of preparation” or “Ready for meal”).</p>	<p>Environmental, nutrition and health, socio-economic indicators</p>	<p>A mix of all, according to the attributes described in each monthly sheet</p>

Figure 10: sample skeleton of the VeriFish calendar

6.6. “Fishy businesses” flash card game

Format	Branding	How to access	Licence	Regional approach
Printable	VeriFish label White label	Link from the VeriFish website Link from the VeriFish Mobile App Available at distributing stakeholders’ places Distributed via retailers even for commercialisation	CC-BY-4	No

Format: A game similar to “Exploding kittens” will be designed including 56 standard-sized cards (63x88 mm), including action, sustainability factsheet, and comic-style hazard cards. The set will be available as a high-quality printable PDF (A4 layout) with ready to cut cards and a rules sheet. The format supports both classroom use and public engagement events, and could be adapted as a digital board/card game.

Branding: All visual assets including cards, rules, and optional printable box templates are designed to reflect a playful comic identity while aligning with the VeriFish visual identity. The VeriFish logo and the European Commission funding acknowledgement will be included, while a white label version of the game will be made available for schools, museums, and organisations wishing to distribute the game under their own initiative and logo. Users who co-brand the game are encouraged to notify the VeriFish consortium and share re-use details.

Accessibility: The game files will be made accessible on the VeriFish website and Mobile App for download in multiple formats. Printed copies can be provided upon request, upon budget availability.

Target group:

- Creators: SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens (ages 3 to 99)

6.6.1. How to address sustainability

Purpose: the game will be designed to inform players, especially children and families, about the sustainability of marine species in a fun and engaging way.

Number of games: 1

Language versions: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
<p>A card game for raising awareness about responsible seafood choices and the importance of marine ecosystems. Through comic-style illustrations and interactive gameplay, the game introduces players to real world marine species and the potential impact of fishing practices. Each Species Card features factual data on a species sustainability and nutritional status, based on criteria such as overfishing risk, bycatch, and nutritional value. Players learn to identify fisheries that are assessed to be more sustainable using an infographics design. The game supports ocean literacy, and is ideal for use in schools, aquariums, and outreach activities aiming to build a generation of informed, sustainability minded citizens. The game will include:</p> <p>20 Species Cards: fish species illustrated in comic style, each with sustainability coming from the VeriFish indicator framework scoring system and species information as included in the VeriFish factsheet, + others considered relevant for consumers' point of view (see D3.2)</p> <p>Action cards: such as peek ahead, reshuffle, swap, and block, which give players powerful ways to outsmart opponents. The actions will refer to the attributes from the 3 sustainability pillars on environment, social and economic and nutrition and health and will invite the player to behave responsibly to get points</p> <p>Wild card: complete any combination or replace any species card. Wild cards will focus on aquaculture species and will include informative text to read</p> <p>The game instructions will clearly mention the sources of data and information included in the cards.</p>	Environmental, nutrition and health, socio-economic indicators	A mix of all, according to the cards to be designed

Figure 11: Example of a draft mockup of Fishy businesses cards - the image is purely indicative

6.7. Map of fishery puzzle

Format	Branding	How to access	Licence	Regional approach
Virtual Printable	VeriFish label White label	Link from the VeriFish website Link from the VeriFish Mobile App Available at distributing stakeholders' places Distributed via retailers even for commercialisation	CC-BY-4	No

Format: VeriFish Puzzle will be designed as an interactive tool designed to foster curiosity about where seafood is caught (i.e. ocean, lake, or river) and facilitate reading of labels on fish products. The puzzle will come in versions ranging from 100 to 500 pieces (according to the age of the target players), and can also be adapted into a digital interactive map.

Branding: The puzzle will be designed in line with the VeriFish visual identity, using colorful, comic-style illustrations that appeal to younger audiences while ensuring added value. Each version will include the VeriFish logo and the European Commission funding acknowledgement. A white label version of the game will be made available for schools, museums, and organisations wishing to distribute with their logo, while maintaining recognition of the original project. Users who co-brand the game are encouraged to notify the VeriFish consortium and share re-use details.

Accessibility: VeriFish Puzzle will be available in both physical and digital formats. A **digital version** will be freely accessible on the VeriFish website and Mobile App, adapted to a format for classroom screens

or tablets, and enriched with clickable links to factsheets and FAO zone explanations. **Printed versions** will be made available upon request, printed on durable, eco-friendly materials suitable for classroom use, subject budget availability. For organisations wishing to co-brand the puzzle or make it more relevant locally (e.g. translating texts, adding specific local species or zones), a customisable version will be offered, too.

Target group:

- Creators: SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators and SG4: European Citizens (ages 3 to 99)

6.7.1. How to address sustainability

Purpose: VeriFish Puzzle will be designed to inform users about the origins of seafood and the FAO areas through an engaging, hands-on format that turns complex topics into playful exploration.

Target groups:

- SG2: Consumers and consumer associations
- Recipients: SG3: Children via parents and educators

Number of puzzles: 1

Language versions: 7

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
<p>The puzzle features a world map and ocean-themed layout with FAO Fishing Zones, which often appear on seafood labels in supermarkets (e.g. “FAO 27” or “FAO 76”), helping individuals understand what these labels mean as they appear in products in supermarkets; illustrations of commonly consumed fish species in Europe and around the world, linked to their native habitats and fishing zones. Seafloor and ecosystem zones, highlighting areas that are ecologically sensitive, overexploited, or under environmental stress, can be added. The game allows players to locate these zones on the world map, connect them to specific species, and learn more about each species.</p> <p>The visual of the puzzle will have:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VeriFish 25 species positioned to their real FAO areas coupled with information from the species factsheet 	<p>Environmental, nutrition and health, socio-economic indicators</p>	<p>GRSF, Wikimedia API, FishBase, SeaLifeBase, STECF</p>

Description	VeriFish related indicators	Data Sources
(D3.2) and the Tier 1 scoring as resulting from the VeriFish ranking <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive learning opportunities, with info-boxes to highlight VeriFish sustainability pillars and their attributes, in a Q&A format (“Did you know that?”) 		

6.8. Board game

The VeriFish consortium is also considering designing a board game. A draft idea develops around a player who steps into the shoes of a conscious seafood consumer trying to make the most responsible, healthy, and sustainable choices at the fish market. But the path to a sustainable basket is far from easy! The player must sift through confusing labels, misleading claims, hidden hazards, and unpredictable events — all while competing against other players who are trying to build the best seafood selection themselves. In a lively, realistic seafood market setting, players move freely between different stands — from local fishmongers to organic markets and online stores — choosing what to buy, verifying what’s real, and outsmarting misinformation.

The player will need sharp thinking, a bit of luck, and a good eye for true sustainability if you want to win

Tentative title: Navigate the Sea of Choices. Find the Truth Behind Your Plate.
<p>Brief Explanation:</p> <p>VeriFish is a strategic family board game for 2–6 players, mixing tactical card collection, market navigation, player interaction, and critical thinking about real-world seafood issues. Players collect Seafood Product cards with attached Label and Origin cards, trying to maximize their points based on sustainability, nutrition, and authenticity.</p> <p>Beware: unverified products might hide problems, and opponents might attack you with misinformation cards!</p> <p>The game ends when one of the market decks runs out — and the player with the most points from their verified, sustainable seafood basket wins.</p> <p>Simple to learn, rich to master — and packed with real-world lessons about the food we eat. Will you spot the fake labels? Will your seafood be local, healthy, and responsibly sourced? Or will you fall victim to fraud and fake news from the deep?</p> <p>Short explanation (for the box or website):</p>

"In VeriFish, become a smart seafood shopper! Navigate markets, verify products, dodge fake labels, and build the most sustainable, healthy seafood basket to win. Fun, strategy, and real-world inspiration combined in one game!"

VeriFish Board Game (Working Title)

Element	Choice
Main Objective	Build the best sustainable seafood basket while navigating a sea of misinformation.
Player Role	Consumers
Resources	Species cards, labels, origin/production methods, hazard/misinformation cards.
Scoring system	Points-based (since VeriFish scoring system is not finalized yet).
Game duration	45–60 minutes standard mode; optional 20–30 minutes quick mode
Solo play?	No (only 2–6 players).
Tone	Realistic seafood market (real fish species, real labels, real locations).

Core Mechanics

Turn Structure:

- Draw Phase
 - Draw a card (Seafood Product, Label, Origin, Misinformation/Hazard).
- Market Phase
 - Choose to Buy, Discard, or Exchange a seafood product.
 - You can combine Seafood + Label + Origin cards to create a Product Bundle.
- Verification Phase
 - Check if your product is sustainable, healthy, legal.
 - If yes → gain Points!
 - If risky/fake → Penalty or lose Points!
- Event Phase (optional)
- Draw an Event Card (e.g., "Misinformation spreads" or "New Eco-Label Introduced").

Player Interaction

- Steal Action: Play a Hazard Card to steal a seafood card from another player ("Spread Fake News: steal a product under investigation!")

- Misinformation Attack: Force a misinformation card onto another player ("Push misleading label story!")
- Market Block: Temporarily close a stand (e.g., supermarket under "label fraud investigation", making it inaccessible for 1 turn).
- End of Turn

Basic Card Types:

Card type	What it does
Seafood Species Card	Gives basic data: species name, nutrition level, sustainability rating (hidden until verified!).
Label Card	Can boost or ruin seafood points (real labels vs fake labels).
Origin/Production Card	Wild-caught, aquaculture, local, imported, etc. Influences sustainability.
Misinformation/Hazard Card	Bad luck! Forces a penalty unless you counter it.
Event Cards	Random good/bad effects for all players (e.g., public trust collapse, new certification success).

How to Win:

At the end of the game:

- You sum the points from your collected verified sustainable seafood bundles.
- Highest total points wins.
- Bonuses for: best nutrition basket, most eco-friendly selection, avoided most hazards.

Board Design Proposal

Imagine a circular market layout with 4 Stands (they are the "zones" on the board):

Stand	Specialities
Local fishmonger	Easier to find high-quality fresh seafood (but less variety).
Supermarket	Wider selection, but higher risk of misinformation or low-quality labels.
Organic Market	Mostly certified products but very limited stock.
Online Market Surprise	sometimes you find premium products, sometimes you get "label fakes"!

First Card Categories Draft

Card type	Description	Example
Seafood Product Card	Fish/shellfish species with hidden sustainability and nutrition score (until verified).	"Atlantic Cod", "European Mussel", "Farmed Tiger Prawn"
Label Card	Positive (MSC, ASC, Organic) or Negative (Fake Eco-labels).	"Real MSC Certification" / "Fake Dolphin-Safe Label"
Origin Card	Local, Regional, Imported. Changes scoring!	"Caught in Atlantic (local)", "Farmed in Southeast Asia"
Hazard/Misinformation Card	Penalties or attack cards.	"Mercury Contamination Alert", "Fake Origin Exposed"
Event Card	Random good/bad events	"New Eco-Award: Bonus points for certified seafood!", "Climate Impact: Local supplies drop"

Core Gameplay

Feature	Design
Movement	Free choice each turn (players can pick the stand they want to visit).
Decks	4 Market Decks (one per stand) + 1 General Deck (Events, Hazards, Misinformation, Attack cards).
Goal	Maximize points by collecting and verifying the best seafood baskets. Strategy depends on where you go and what you collect.
Player Interaction	Use Event and Hazard cards to slow down or disrupt others (e.g., fake labels, scandals, food safety issues).

Basic Turn Structure

Each Turn:

1. Move Phase:
 - a. Move freely to any stand.
2. Draw Phase:

- a. Draw 1 card from the chosen stand deck.
- b. Optionally draw 1 card from the General Event Deck.
3. Action Phase (choose 1):
 - a. Build a Product Bundle (Seafood + Label + Origin).
 - b. Verify one of your unverified products.
 - c. Attack another player (if you have an Attack card).
 - d. Trade one product with another player.
4. Event Phase:
 - a. Resolve Event effects if drawn.
5. End of Turn:
 - a. Check hand limit (max 7 seafood products).

First Version of Points System

Category	Points Earned
Seafood Species	Base points (3–7 depending on sustainability & nutrition level, after verification).
Correct Labels (e.g. MSC)	+3 bonus points.
Fake Labels	-5 points if not spotted!
Local Origin	+2 bonus points (low carbon footprint).
Illegal Products	-8 points (if caught later by an Event!).
Misinformation Cards	Force player to lose points or discard products unless they have a "Verification Token" (optional expansion mechanic).
Perfect Basket Bonus	+10 bonus points if you have products covering diversity (1 shellfish + 1 local fish + 1 aquaculture product, for example).

Example of Decks

Stand	Deck Type	Special Characteristics
Local Fishmonger	Fresh Seafood Deck	High sustainability, lower variety, less risk
Supermarket	Commercial seafood deck	Medium sustainability, many imported products, more risk of fraud

Stand	Deck Type	Special Characteristics
Organic Market	Certified Products Deck	Mostly high-scoring cards but very limited stock (small deck)
Online market	Mixed Deck	Surprise cards, some premium, some disasters (fake products, wrong origins)
General Deck	Event, Attack, Misinformation	Global effects (everyone affected) and attacks against players.

First Mini-Map Layout

[Local Fishmonger]

|

[Organic Market] — Central Market Square — [Supermarket]

|

[Online Market]

Deck piles on each Stand. General Deck in center.

Players can move freely between stands!

Quick Visualization of the Player Area

Each player will have:

- Basket Zone (5 product slots max)
- Attached Labels/Origins
- Unverified / Verified Tokens on products
- Discard Pile for rejected/misinformed seafood
- Points Tracker

Finalized Core Rules

Element	Decision
Basket Size	Players may hold up to 7 cards (seafood products only) at any time. Labels and Origin cards must be attached immediately and do not count toward the limit.

Element	Decision
Verification System	Products are drawn unverified. Players must take a Verification Action (spend a turn OR use a Verification Event/Token) to reveal real sustainability and nutrition scores.
Endgame Trigger	The game ends when any one of the Stand Decks (Local, Supermarket, Organic, Online) or the General Event Deck runs out. Then all players finish the current round and calculate final scores.

Quick summary of "Verification"

Verification Type	Effect
Spend a Turn	Skip market movement and action to verify 1 product.
Play a Verification Event Card	Instantly verify 1 or 2 products.
Special Stand Effect (Organic Market)	All purchases from Organic Market are auto-verified immediately.

6.8.1. Other ideas for board games

Other possible game concepts could be developed around:

- i) **Explorers:** players become sustainable seafood explorers, racing across global oceans to collect and trade marine species while learning about sustainability, and the impact of fishing practices. The mission is to build the most sustainable seafood business.
- ii) **Fishers:** players race from the oceans / seas up to land and complete a sustainable fishery journey, by collecting points any time they positively assess one of the attributes from the VeriFish pillar indicators. Those who assess all the majority of attributes in the 3 pillars wins. The winner is the player who completes the journey with the most sustainable collection of species, balancing nutrition and biodiversity while avoiding overfished stocks and illegal catches. The board game will stimulate players to travel around a world map-style board, visiting fishing zones (e.g. FAO regions), local markets, and marine protected areas, collecting fish species cards with different sustainability scores, taking sustainability actions and making choices that impact their overall "ocean health score."

7. Promotion and distribution channels

Promotion of these media products will be achieved through active engagement with education channels, associations, NGOs and national seafood product boards that can help distribute materials via their online and in-person networks. The goal is to maximise reach of these products, encouraging their adoption, further distribution, and re-use. Media products will be distributed under CCBY licences to promote reuse, ensuring future replicability and sustainability. In addition to promotion via the VeriFish Community of Practice, an initial list of multiplier channels is listed below, with different dissemination, distribution and promotional objectives who will be contacted for further suggestions regarding reuse.

Channel	Type	Description	Website
EXPLODING KITTEN PROVIDERS	Commercial provider	Exploding Kittens is a private company based in Los Angeles, CA, USA. The company offers over a dozen games and expansions available and it can be contacted to also co-design and commercialise the VeriFish version of their game. Engagement channels also include their fan communities on Discord and Reddit	https://exploding-kittens.gorgias.help/en-US/contact
Fishtales	Foundation	The Fish Tales Foundation runs various projects around the world that contribute to making small-scale fisheries and fish farms more sustainable. In particular, they focus on fishing communities in developing countries. By partnering with Fish Tales VeriFish can increase Tear 2 data and co-create the media products, recipes and video trailers. VeriFish EAB member Irene Kranendonk is Impact Manager at Fish Tales and Board Member at the Fish Tales Foundation.	https://www.fish-tales.com/en
Oceana	NGO	Oceana is one of the most relevant and influential ocean-related NGOs globally, and also in the EU. For example, they established Global Fishing Watch in a partnership with Google and SkyTruth. They are pretty dark-green and do a lot of campaigning Greenpeace-style. However, they also have a strong research and policy team. In Brussels one of their focus areas is transparency & traceability. They are also one of the most prominent IUU fighters.	https://www.instagram.com/oceana/

Channel	Type	Description	Website
FishChoice	NGO	Small environmental non profit Organisation based in USA founded in 2008 that envisions a thriving and sustainable global seafood industry. It developed FishChoice.com, an interactive platform that tailors the seafood sustainability information businesses need, and makes it accessible and actionable. The mission is very similar to the VeriFish web-app and a collaboration with FishChoice can facilitate the engagement with sustainable seafood industry actors. EAB member Paul Bulcock is Aquaculture Information Manager at Sustainable Fisheries Partnership	Website: https://fishchoice.com/
Ocean Wise	NGO	Ocean Wise seafood program is part of the Global Seafood Ratings Alliance (GSRA). The GSRA is an alliance of sustainable seafood NGOs from five continents across the world who help each other to improve sustainability globally. VeriFish media products can be distributed via Ocean Wise Ocean Education projects.	https://ocean.org/blog/sustainable-seafood-guides-from-our-international-ngo-partners/
Seafood Watch	NGO	The Monterey Bay Aquarium launched Seafood Watch in 1999 as a special exhibit about the impacts of seafood. The program and its scope has grown over the past 25 years. Today, their science-based assessments are a primary resource for understanding sustainable seafood around the world. Seafood Watch can help VeriFish reach North American Consumers.	https://www.seafoodwatch.org/
Sustainable Ocean Alliance	NGO	Sustainable Ocean Alliance (SOA) is a global nonprofit organization created by youth—for youth—dedicated to activating young people, developing and implementing innovative solutions, and mobilizing an ocean workforce to restore the health of the ocean in our lifetime. SOA has grown into the world’s largest network of young ocean leaders, innovators, and policymakers	https://www.soalliance.org/

Channel	Type	Description	Website
Blue Marine Foundation	NGO	Blue Marine is dedicated to creating marine reserves and establishing sustainable models of fishing. Its mission is to campaign against over-fishing and for the effective protection of 30% of the world's oceans by 2030.	https://www.bluemarinefoundation.com/
Catchwelfare platform	NGO	The catch welfare platform is an industry-science driven platform to create pragmatic solutions to improve catch welfare. The primary objective is to establish and coordinate the Catch Welfare Platform (CWP), a network of multidisciplinary teams aimed at expediting the transition in world fisheries towards practices and technologies that enhance the welfare of the catch, including post-capture slaughter. VeriFish partner Michelle Boonstra is the project manager of the Catch Welfare Platform.	https://catchwelfareplatform.com
BlueMissionMed	Other / projects	BlueMissionMed will engage stakeholders from Policy, Business, Research&Innovation and Civil Society, as well as the so-called Ecosystem Enablers to synergize the actions of the Mission Lighthouse in the Mediterranean basin.	https://bluemissionmed.eu/
ResponSEable project	Other / projects	They developed a number of media products for different type of stakeholders, including citizens. Useful to disseminate the media products.	https://responseable.acteon-environment.eu/
Bioviva Foundation	Other / projects	Bioviva Foundation aims at educating children around the world who are in a situation of exclusion, through fun and educational tools, fostering self-respect, respect for others and respect for life with all its diversity. VeriFish media products will be proposed to Bioviva Foundation in white label for uptake.	https://www.bioviva.com/en/foundation
Consorzio Pescatori di Goro	Consumers and consumer associations	The cooperative, leader in the shellfish sector and markets at Italian and European level.	https://www.copego.it/il-consorzio.html

Channel	Type	Description	Website
CRIOC (Centre de Recherche et d'Information des Organisations de Consommateurs)	Consumers and consumer associations	CRIOC carries out scientific studies and analyzes at the request of the various committees and working groups, the consumer organizations and the Federal Public Service Work, Economy and Consumers. Topics covered include consumer perception and behavior patterns when purchasing or using goods or services, as well as purchasing power, advertising and sustainable consumption.	https://www.oeco.be/fr
ECU (European Consumers Union)	Consumers and consumer associations	ECU aims at unifying European consumer organizations for collaborating on all matters related to consumerism and on the pan-European citizenship.	https://europeanconsumersunion.eu/?lang=en
Federconsumatori	Consumers and consumer associations	Non-profit association whose priority objectives are the information and protection of consumers and users.	https://www.federconsumatori.it/
EUFIC	Consumers and consumer associations	The European Food Information Council (EUFIC), is a consumer-oriented non-profit organisation, founded to make the science behind food and health more accessible and easier to understand among the public.	https://www.eufic.org/en/
The Oceans and Seafood Markets Initiative (OSMI)	Consumers and consumer associations	collaboration between four nonprofits, with the common goal of improving seafood traceability. The Oceansand SeafoodMarketsInitiative (OSMI) is part of the Conservation and Markets Initiatives (CMI) portfolio.	https://www.futureoffish.org/
The Marine Diaries	NGO	The Marine Diaries is part of the EU4Ocean Coalition , set up by the European Commission. This coalition aims to increase Ocean Literacy across Europe. The Marine Diaries can help disseminating VeriFish media products and co-creating video trailers and SoMe campaigns	https://www.themarinediaries.com/mission
Marine Conservation Society	NGO	The Marine Conservation Society is a UK-based charitable organisation working with businesses, governments and communities to clean and protect oceans.	https://www.mcsuk.org/

Channel	Type	Description	Website
Ireland Explorers education programme	Research and Academia	The Marine Institute’s Explorers Education Programme engages with primary schools, teachers, children and the education network, creating marine leaders and ocean champions in Ireland.	https://www.marine.ie/site-area/areas-activity/education-outreach/explorers-education-programme
Ocean Conservancy	NGO	NGO at the forefront of ocean conservation	https://oceanconservancy.org/
Blue School	Children	The Blue Schools project was an Erasmus project to introduce the Blue Economy to school education and support students to be aware of the blue economy and culture and learn how to build a sustainable future in coastal areas	https://www.blue-schools.eu/en/home-3/
Conservation Alliance for Seafood Solutions members	NGO	NGO representing over 185 organizations across 30 countries, all committed to improving how seafood is produced, sold, and consumed worldwide. VeriFish EAB Richard Stavis is Chair of the Conservation Alliance Board.	https://solutionsforseafood.org/

8. Next steps

The next phase of development for the VeriFish Media Products involves finalising concepts in detail, such as defining all gameplay and target age groups. Based on the insights collected in this report, we will proceed with the design and creation of early prototypes, which will be tested in practical settings (e.g. workshops, outreach events) to evaluate both engagement and learning impact and which will be subject to other requirements gathering and feedback sessions with selected members of the Community of Practice. The first one planned during the VeriFish consortium meeting in Copenhagen, 24-26 June 2025, with the participation of the members of the External Advisory Board, while a second one might be organised during the annual conference of the CatchWelfare platform. Feedback from these activities will guide refinement toward fully operational print & play and/or digital version of the products. Afterwards products will be designed and published on the Verifish channels (website, app and outreach channels), and distributed to the identified promotional channels for further re-use, re-brand and distribution.